

DIAMAS

Developing Institutional Open Access
Publishing Models to Advance
Scholarly Communication

D4.5 IPSP Registry

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Consortium overview

AMU	UNIVERSITE D'AIX MARSEILLE	FR
PVM	PROTISVALOR MEDITERRANEE SAS	FR
OPERAS	OPEN ACCESS IN THE EUROPEAN AREA THROUGH SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION	BE
CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	FR
EIFL	STICHTING EIFL.NET	NL
FECYT	FUNDACION ESPANOLA PARA LA CIENCIA Y LA TECNOLOGIA, F.S.P., FECYT	ES
TSV	TIETEELLISTEN SEURAIN VALTUUSKUNNASTA	FI
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
UB	UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA	ES
UniZD	SVEUCILISTE U ZADRU	HR
FFZG	SVEUCILISTE U ZAGREBU FILOZOFSKI FAKULTET	HR
Science Europe	SCIENCE EUROPE	BE
EUA	ASSOCIATION EUROPEENNE DE L'UNIVERSITES	BE
OASPA	STICHTING OPEN ACCESS SCHOLARLY PUBLISHERS ASSOCIATON	NL
UiT	UNIVERSITETET I TROMSOE - NORGES ARKTISKE UNIVERSITET	NO
CNR	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	IT

UGOE	GEORG-AUGUST-UNIVERSITÄT GÖTTINGEN STIFTUNG ÖFFENTLICHEN RECHTS	DE
SPE	STICHTING SPARC EUROPE	NL
UU	UNIVERSITEIT UTRECHT	NL
EKT	ETHNIKO KENTRO TEKMIROSIS KAI ILEKTRONIKOU PERIECHOMENOU	EL
IBL PAN	INSTYTUT BADAN LITERACKICH POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK	PL
ESF	FONDATION EUROPEENNE DE LA SCIENCE	FR
JISC	JISC LBG	UK
DOAJ	INFRASTRUCTURE SERVICES FOR OPEN ACCESS C I C	UK

Document overview

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Acronyms

AEUP	Association of European University Presses
API	Application Programming Interface
CMS	Content Management System
CRAFT-OA	Creating a Robust Accessible Federated Technology for Open Access
DDH	Diamond Discovery Hub
DOAS	Diamond Open Access Standard
EASE	European Association of Science Editors
EDCH	European Diamond Capacity Hub
ERA	European Research Area
ERAC	European Research Area and Innovation Committee
FTE	Full-time Equivalent
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
IFLA	International Federation of Libraries Associations
IPSP	Institutional Publisher(s) and Service Provider(s)
IPTP	Institutional Publishing Tools and Technology Provider(s)
NCC	National Capacity Centre
OA	Open Access
PHP	Hypertext Preprocessor
PID	Process Identifier

ROR	Research Organisation Registry
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
SSO	Single Sign-on
UI	User Interface
XML	Extensible Markup Language

Executive Summary

This report documents the implementation of the EDCH Registry (<https://registry.diamas.org/>) and Forum (<https://forum.diamas.org/>), two digital platforms developed as part of the DIAMAS Task 4.5 “Collaborative Tools for IPSPs”.

These platforms serve as virtual venues to support the interaction of the network of Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSPs) and Institutional Publishing Tools and Technology Providers (IPTPs) active in the Diamond Open Access ecosystem.

The Registry serves as a central information hub, mapping organisations involved in Diamond OA publishing. It supports collaboration by providing structured data on the services and infrastructures available in the European Research Area. The Forum is designed as an interactive space for community-building and peer exchange within the Diamond OA landscape. It enables knowledge sharing, dialogue, and coordination among diverse stakeholders.

The report presents the conceptual and technical design of both platforms. It defines their scope, identifies the primary user groups, and details the processes and frameworks guiding their development. Additionally, the report outlines the strategies used to promote community engagement and visibility and concludes with a roadmap to ensure the platforms’ long-term viability and relevance.

The report is also published on Zenodo, and can be accessed at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15433338>

1. Introduction

This report presents the development of the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH) Registry(<https://registry.diamas.org/>) and Forum(<https://forum.diamas.org/>), the main deliverables of DIAMAS Task 4.5. These two platforms serve as foundational components of the network of Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSPs) and Institutional Publishing Tools and Technology Providers (IPTPs) involved in Diamond Open Access (OA) initiatives, which was established jointly by the DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA projects.

As a core part of the IPSP/IPTP network, the Forum facilitates interaction among the Diamond OA community, and serves as an online venue for knowledge and information exchange. The Registry promotes collaboration among various institutions by offering up-to-date information on their operations and capacities.

The report outlines the conceptual framework and technical processes behind the development of the Registry and the Forum. Section 2 defines their scope and targeted stakeholder groups. Section 3 details the development of the Registry, including the overall methodological framework, technical specifications, structural components, user roles, and registration workflow. Section 4 describes the organisational structure of the Forum, and specifically aspects related to user and content management, as well as moderation mechanisms for fostering productive discussions. Section 5 outlines the adopted dissemination and engagement strategy, and presents the outcomes of the communication campaign. Finally, section 6 outlines the plan for ensuring the long-term sustainability of both the Registry and the Forum.

2. Scope and membership of the EDCH Registry and Forum

The DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA projects are working closely together to establish a network of Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSP) and Institutional Publishing Tools & Technology Providers (IPTP), with an aim to strengthen collaboration among organisations and individuals engaged in Diamond OA initiatives across Europe (Paulhac et al., 2025).

The Registry and the Forum are the main building blocks of the IPSP/IPTP network. The Registry serves as the main entry point to the network and provides information on the expertise and operational capacities of its member institutions. Within the network, the Forum constitutes a dynamic space for the broader Diamond OA community to connect, establish partnerships, and exchange good practices; it functions as both a collaboration venue and a conversational space where individuals can share information and collectively address challenges.

2.1 Stakeholders and target audiences

As part of the conceptual design of the network, a joint working group from the DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA projects has developed the following typology to identify the organisations that qualify for inclusion in the network:

Institutional Publishing Tools & Technology Providers (IPTP): Any entity that provides tools and/or technologies such as standards, code, hardware and software that enable any user and service provider to perform specific tasks or operations to achieve their objectives. Such tools and technologies include, but are not limited to, publishing software, format converters, XML and content structuration standards, peer review management systems, editing tools, PIDs, data exchange protocols.

Institutional Publishers and Service Providers (IPSP): Any entity that provides services and/or infrastructure to authors and publishers for scholarly publishing. These services may be provided by the institutional publisher itself (in which case the institutional publisher is also the IPSP) or by other entities inside or outside the institution. Such activities include, but are not limited to: (a) editorial activities (selection of manuscripts, peer-review, etc.); (b) operational activities (production activities like copy editing, proofreading, type-setting, creating metadata), IT activities, communication activities (marketing/dissemination, social media, etc.), as well as administrative and financial activities (contracts, accounting, documentation, etc.).

The definitions of IPSP/IPTP apply at the level of organisations, which are invited to create a profile in the Registry. The participation of other stakeholders, such as funders and policymakers, is currently under discussion. However, it should be noted that many of the entities identified as either IPSP or IPTP have multiple roles within the scholarly publishing landscape and are actively involved in policy making and Diamond OA funding initiatives (Arasteh et al., 2025).

Accordingly, within these organisations, various professionals are involved in a broad spectrum of activities and initiatives, including publishing, providing support and services to publishers, and establishing policy and funding frameworks at institutional level. A main objective of the Forum is to engage and onboard those individuals into an online community and, through their active engagement, ensure broad representation of their respective organisations.

To address the diversity within the Diamond OA landscape, the IPSP/IPTP network emerges as an organisational framework that allows its member organisations to showcase their multiple roles, and individuals to actively engage in discussions relevant to their areas of expertise. The targeted professional profiles and entities include, but are not limited to:

- Directors and managers of publishing services (Forum)
- Publishing professionals, staff providing support (e.g. librarians), and editors of Diamond OA journals, books, and other research outputs (Forum)
- Research managers and researchers with an interest in Diamond OA publishing (Forum)
- Organisations responsible for preparing, producing, and distributing scholarly content to the public (Registry)
- Entities providing infrastructure and managing workflows for scholarly publishing (Registry)
- Providers of software, standards, and technological solutions used in scholarly publishing (Registry)

3. The EDCH Registry

3.1 Methodology

This section outlines the implementation timeline and key methodological considerations involved in the design and development of the Registry.

3.1.1 Selection of platform

The Registry has been developed on a Drupal-based installation,

Drupal was chosen because it is a reliable open-source solution with an active community that supports its ongoing development. It also offers flexible tools for managing of content and workflows by moderators who do not have advanced technical skills.

Specifically, as a Content Management System (CMS) Drupal allows the creation and combination of custom content types required for the setting up of virtual entities. These fields constitute the organisational profiles in the Registry, integrating various types of information (names, locations, services provided, supported languages, and more).

Drupal also supports the definition of tags and categories that have been applied to create a taxonomy of organisations and their activities, and facilitates the interaction of users with the Registry by providing advanced search and filtering options. Additional features such as the responsive design make the public interface accessible to a broader audience and improve the overall user experience.

With regards to information management, Drupal is interoperable with external databases and installations – a feature that in future iterations will allow information retrieval via the main EDCH page (diamas.org), and the Registry's potential synchronisation with other portals with similar content and scope. Additionally, it supports analytics and tracking features that allow the administrators to monitor user engagement and the overall usage of the Registry.

Finally, Drupal's integrated user management system is based on variable user roles and permissions that allow administrators to grant controlled editing rights to authenticated users. This facilitates profile management for registered organisations, by allowing designated users within each organisation to update the details of the respective registered entity.

3.1.2 Implementation timeline

Phase 1: Conceptual design and technical specifications

The conceptual design of the Registry is based on an online workflow for creating, publishing, and updating organisational profiles. The first phase of implementation focused on identifying the elements of the organisational profile and the technical features required to associate individual users with organisations, grant them rights to manage the respective profiles, and assign administrators with permissions to manage users and registered profiles.

The overall structure of the profile was shaped based on the findings of the DIAMAS survey (Armengou et al. 2023), which captured data from 43 countries and mapped the landscape of institutional publishing within the European Research Area (ERA). The survey revealed a wide range of practices, levels of capacity, and strong interest among IPSPs and IPTPs in collaborating on technical services, support, production, and communication. In response to these insights, the organisational profiles were designed to offer a comprehensive overview of an organisation's activities, areas of expertise, services, and operational capacities.

The elements of the organisational profile were informed by the contents of the "IPSP Database" (Agnoloni et al., 2023) that complemented the DIAMAS survey report; it contains organisational data and a set of practical recommendations for the development of the Registry, which helped identify both its conceptual structure and online workflows. Based on these recommendations – which ranged from providing clear and detailed instructions to users and identifying a set of minimum mandatory fields to ensure relevance of the profiles, to practical suggestions that would enhance usability – several features were introduced to improve consistency and clarity. Additional fields were incorporated to highlight the capacities and activities of organisations and increase their visibility; controlled vocabularies and advanced search functionalities were developed; and editorial oversight was emphasised to ensure the accuracy and currency of submitted information.

Other registries – such as the Research Organisation Registry (ROR) (<https://ror.org/>) and the IFLA Library Map of the World (<https://librarymap.ifla.org/>) – were reviewed to inform the structure of the profiles.

In parallel, the main stages of the organisation management workflow were defined (further described in section 3.2).

Phase 2: Development and testing

The second phase of implementation involved technical tasks to develop a functional prototype of the Registry. The IPSP database was uploaded to a mockup platform launched on a development server, and used to implement functionalities such as user

registration, data retrieval and updating. During this stage, user roles (regular users, moderators, and administrators, as described in section 3.2.3) and a moderation workflow—coordinated by consortium partners—were also defined. Additionally, informational texts, a comprehensive set of guidelines, and a glossary were compiled to support users (see Appendix 1).

The alpha version of the Registry was launched as a subdomain of the EDCH (registry.diamas.org) in January 2025. The platform’s functionalities were tested by a small group of consortium members, who were asked either to update their organisation’s profile (if it was included in the pre-populated database), or create a new organisational profile. Extensive tests corresponding to use cases defined during the previous phase were also conducted by the team of developers.

Phase 3: Rollout and launch

In March 2025 the Registry was updated to a beta version. As part of this transition, a group of DIAMAS partners were assigned as administrators to conduct profile submission reviews, and provide support to users of the platform. Before the public launch of the Registry, the administrators revisited and updated the informational texts as well as the criteria for an organisation’s inclusion in the Registry. Live testing sessions among the administrators were also organised to evaluate the flow of the registration process.

The live version of the Registry was officially launched on 2 May 2025, at which point the DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA consortia were invited to register.

3.1.3 Criteria for inclusion

To ensure relevance with the scope and values of the EDCH, all organisations listed in the Registry must meet the following criteria for inclusion:¹

1. Be actively involved in Diamond OA initiatives, either as Publishers, Service Providers, or Tools and Technology Providers.
Relevance: This criterion ensures that only Publishers, Service Providers, Tools and Technology Providers evidently involved in and contributing to the Diamond Open Access publishing ecosystem are included, creating a community committed to equitable access to scholarly content.
2. Demonstrate a commitment to community ownership: their governance structures should reflect control by and for the scholarly community, particularly

¹The criteria are also published on the Registry website: <https://registry.diamas.org/criteria-inclusion-registry>

researchers and academics. For-profit entities can only qualify as Service Providers, if they directly support Diamond OA Publishers.

Relevance: Emphasising community ownership of the Publisher, Service Provider, or Tools and Technology Provider ensures that the publishing process remains accessible, equitable, and aligned with the values of Diamond OA, promoting collaboration and shared responsibility among stakeholders.

3. Be public legal entities, including non-profit organisations, academic institutions, government bodies, or for-profit entities that support Diamond OA. Individual journals are not eligible, as the Registry hosts organisations.

Additionally, for-profit entities that monetise scientific publishing can only qualify as Service Providers if they support Diamond OA publishing

Relevance: Understanding the legal status of a Publisher, Service Provider, or Tools and Technology Provider provides insights into its objectives, funding sources, and governance. This is crucial for determining whether the Publisher, Service Provider, or Tools and Technology Provider aligns with the principles of Diamond OA, which typically favours non-profit models.

4. Be part of the European research landscape: either by being located in, or governed by a parent entity located in, a country belonging to the European Research Area (ERA) or acting as an observer to the European Research Area and Innovation Committee (ERAC).

3.1.4 Moderation

The main aspects of the moderation framework, as defined during the second phase of implementation, are as follows:

1. **Eligibility assessment:** submitted organisational profiles are reviewed against the inclusion criteria. Organisations that do not meet these criteria are declined, provided with clear, documented justifications, and encouraged to reapply if their circumstances change.
2. **Profile review:** administrators review each submitted profile to verify that all required fields are accurately completed and that the information provided is valid. Users are notified in cases where minor edits (e.g., typographical corrections) are made or if further changes to the profile details are required.
3. **'Ownership' validation:** when a user requests 'ownership' (permission to manage an existing organisational profile - as described in section 3.2.2.1), the current profile 'owner' is asked to validate the request. If the 'owner' does not respond or denies the request, a mediation protocol is initiated to ensure transparency and fairness.

Throughout the registration and update process, standardised email templates are used to facilitate consistent and clear communication with users. These templates cover

requests for missing information, reminders, confirmations of approval, and explanations for submission rejections.

3.2 Technical Implementation

Following the evaluation and acceptance of a proposal to implement the EDCH website, the Toolsuite² and the Registry (Armengou et al., 2024), Pontemedia worked closely with the Registry administrators to design, implement, and test the workflows and core features needed to support content and user management on the platform. The following sections provide a more detailed overview of the technical specifications, workflows, and configurations.

3.2.1 Technical specifications

The Registry is built on Drupal 10, leveraging its modularity and scalability. It currently operates on a server stack comprising PHP 8.3.12, Nginx, and MariaDB, ensuring a stable and high-performing environment. Custom modules have been developed to manage special functions and specific rules unique to the organisation registration workflow, ensuring adherence to the project's requirements:

Scenario-based registration: upon completing their registration, users are guided through one of the following actions based on the organisation information provided:

- Create a new organisational profile, if the organisation details provided during registration do not match an entry in the Registry database.
- Manage an existing organisational profile, if the organisation is listed in the database, but not currently managed by another user.
- Make an 'ownership' claim (i.e. request profile management rights), if the organisation is already registered and managed by another user

Organisation profile management: users whose association with an organisation has been verified can login and update/edit the profile.

Notifications: administrators are notified of new profile submissions, 'ownership' requests, and updates to published profiles. Users with management rights receive notifications when their organisation's profile is published or when an 'ownership' claim is submitted.

Plugins and built-in elements: a range of Drupal modules and plugins were activated to enhance specific functionalities, including:

- Address, Geofield, Leaflet, Leaflet Markercluster, Leaflet Views, to support advanced geographical data management and map-based displays

² The Toolsuite (<https://toolsuite.diamas.org>) provides high-level guidance and resources that will assist Diamond OA publishers and service providers in meeting current standards.

- Computed Field, Computed Address, for dynamic data calculation and address management
- Email Protect, for email address obfuscation and security.
- Geocoder, Geocoder Address, Geocoder Field, Geocoder Geofield, to convert addresses into geographical coordinate
- Webform, Webform Access, Webform Content Creator, Webform Geonames Integration: for form completion, submission management, and integration with content types and geographical data.

Secure communication: The website is served over HTTPS, ensuring secure and encrypted communication between users and online data.

Access control: Appropriate Drupal user roles and granular permissions were set up to restrict access to specific sections and functionalities.

Data integrity and validation: the registration workflow includes automated checks against existing records (published, drafts) to prevent duplicate entries.

Visual design: the visual design, including fonts, colours, and logo variations, adheres to the EDCH guidelines.

3.2.2 Information structure and back-end functionalities

This section outlines the structure and back-end functionalities of the Organisation Registration webform (Annex 2), which serves as the primary data input mechanism for new and updated organisation profiles.

3.2.2.1. Information Structure

Two main content types have been created to input organisational data:

- **Organisation:** this custom content type is used to capture in a structured manner information submitted by users during the organisation registration process. It corresponds to the fields of the "organisation Registration" webform (described below in more detail), which are complemented with additional metadata fields for users identified as "organisation owners".
- **Organisation Bucket:** this custom content type stores pre-populated organisation data collected via the IPSP Database. Its structure corresponds to that of the webform; however, the organisational data is only partially filled, as only a specific subset of fields in the IPSP Database was used. The remaining fields, as well as the details of 'organisation owners,' are automatically completed upon validation of an ownership request.

Both content types have an active field used by administrators to review and modify an organisation's status on the Registry (draft, published).

The 'organisation Registration' webform is structured around four main informational units:

1. **Essential identification:** information about the organisation, including its official name (in the original language and English), acronym, main website URL, official contact email address, and type (Publisher, Service Provider, Tools and/or Technology Provider).
2. **Administrative information and governance:** information about the organisation's legal entity type, parent entity (if any), primary geographical location (country and city), and number of full-time equivalent (FTE) paid staff involved in its operations.
3. **Services and capacities:** information about the services provided or supported with tools and technologies as well as the supported disciplines and languages (languages the services, tools, and outputs are available in).
4. **Synergies and visibility:** as a first step to enable potential interoperability workflows and information exchange between the Registry and other registries/directories, the ID or the profile URL of the organisation in other Registries (e.g. ROR, IFLA Library Map of the World, OPERAS Pathfinder) is also optionally requested; additionally, 'organisation owners' can express their interest in their organisation to become a trusted source (journal metadata provider) for the Diamond Discovery Hub.³

During the organisation registration process, the 'owner' is asked to provide the details of a primary and, optionally, a secondary contact person. The contact details are copied in the webform for future use by (e.g. in case the organisation's profile needs to be modified or updated).

A mandatory checklist is used to verify the accuracy of the submitted information, confirm the user's status as an authorised representative of the organisation, and obtain their consent for the organisation's data to be made publicly available on the Registry website.

3.2.2.2. *Back-end functionalities*

The webform is integrated with the backend features and custom content types listed below, designed to facilitate the management of organisational and user data:

Data capture and storage: all submitted data is stored in a database directly linked to the webform.

³ The Diamond Discovery Hub (DDH) is currently developed by the CRAFT-OA project as a comprehensive registry of institutionally published and scholar-led OA journals in Europe. The profile details of organisations interested in becoming trusted sources are forwarded to the DDH management team, who initiates the process of metadata provision.

Node creation and data linkage: the webform seamlessly creates data entries in the *Organisation* content type using the *webform_content_creator* module that processes submitted data as a structured content node. Initially, new nodes are in a "draft" status.

Conditional logic and States API: Drupal's States API is utilised to control the visibility of form fields based on user selections, ensuring a dynamic experience.

Autocomplete features: integration with Geonames provides autocomplete options for geographical fields (e.g., city names), enhancing data accuracy.

Validation: required fields enforce data completion. Additional custom validation rules are in place for specific fields (e.g., URL format, email domain checks, character restrictions) to ensure data quality.

Pre-population logic: when a user attempts to register an organisation for which data already exists in the *Organisation Bucket* content type, the system automatically pre-populates the webform with as much available data as possible, streamlining the registration process.

Email verification: the "Organisation email address" field of the webform is subject to a separate verification process to confirm its authenticity.

Data mapping: submitted webform data is mapped to corresponding fields of the *Organisation* content type, ensuring proper data structure for display and search.

Geocoding integration: Geocoder modules convert provided country and city information into geographical coordinates (latitude/longitude), to enable displaying an organisation's location on an interactive map.

Status modification: the "Workflows" module is utilised to manage the moderation of an organisation's status (e.g., from "draft" to "published"), requiring administrative action for publication.

3.2.3 User roles and permissions

The Registry employs a structured user management system to manage access to content and functionalities, ensuring customisable levels of control for different user types. The table outlines user roles and corresponding rights:

Role description	Permissions / Rights
Anonymous user: website visitors who are not logged in	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Can view all public content and published organisational profiles - Can search and browse the list of published profiles

<p>Authenticated user: website visitors who have created an account and are logged in</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Can view all public content and published organisational profiles - Can initiate the organisation registration process - Can claim 'ownership' of an organisation in the 'Organisation Bucket' list - Can edit the organisational profile they manage - Can claim 'ownership' of a published (already managed) organisation
<p>Administrator: users with elevated privileges for managing the Drupal backend and website content</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Can manage the Drupal core system, including configurations and modules - Can manage user accounts and roles - Can manage website content (e.g., create, edit, delete any page or organisational profile) - Can publish draft organisations
<p>Admin: a subset of Administrators with additional responsibilities related to content management</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Possesses all permissions of the "Administrator" role. - Additionally, receives notifications regarding: (a) New organisation submissions; (b) requests by authenticated users; (c) organisation profile updates

Table 1. User roles and permissions

3.2.4 Registration process

The organisation registration workflow is initiated by a non-authenticated user who signs up on the Registry platform and proceeds to either create a new organisational profile or request to update an existing one. Users with administrator permissions become involved once a new or edited profile is submitted.

Step 1: Account creation. The user accesses the account creation form (<https://registry.diamas.org/user/register>) and fills out their name, organisational email, organisation details (name, URL, country) and their role within the organisation. A confirmation email is sent by the platform, prompting the user to set their account password.

Step 2: User association with an organisational profile. The system checks whether the organisation details provided during user account creation match an existing entry in either the *Organisation* or *Organisation Bucket* database.

Scenario-based options:

a. The Organisation is registered and has an 'owner': the user is presented with the matching organisation name and given the option to request management rights. The user can request ownership of the profile. In the latter case, emails are sent to the administrators and the current 'owner', who is asked to approve the request. If the request is accepted, the current owner is replaced, loses editing permissions, and the new 'owner' is notified and proceeds to update the organisational profile. If the request is not answered or is denied, the administrators contact the current owner to resolve the issue and proceed accordingly with granting rights or rejecting the request.

The process of shifting 'ownership' was introduced to ensure that each organisation retains an 'owner' who can update its profile - for example, if the previous 'owner' is no longer affiliated with the organisation or has taken a different role within it.

b. The organisation is part of the *Bucket*: the user is presented with the organisation name and the option to request ownership. They can either create a new organisational profile or request management rights for the existing one.

c. The organisation is not found: the user is prompted to create a new organisational profile and is presented with a blank organisation registration form, which they complete and submit.

Step 3: Validation. Submitted organisational profiles remain in draft status. Administrators receive a notification and review the organisation details.

Scenario-Based Options:

a. The organisation does not qualify for inclusion. Administrators inform the user.

b. The organisation qualifies for inclusion.

- The profile does not require edits. Administrators proceed to the next step.
- Administrators contact the 'owner' to request clarifications or edits.
- Administrators make minor edits that do not require user approval (e.g., correcting typos), inform the user about any changes made, and proceed to the next step.

Step 4: Publication and Updates. If the above conditions are met, the administrators manually change the organisation's status from "draft" to "published". The 'owner' receives a notification that their organisation has been published. They can then log into the platform and update the organisation's profile details as needed. The platform

administrators are informed about the profile update, and proceed with reviewing the changes.

3.2.5 Website structure

The public interface of the Registry platform features eight compositional elements, accessible to both non-authenticated and authenticated users. The corresponding informational texts are provided in Annex 1 of the report.

Website structure and contents	
Title - Details	URL
Main page: This page outlines the scope and serves as the primary entry point to the Registry and the Forum.	https://registry.diamas.org/
About: This page provides guidance on user and organisation registration, with links to the corresponding pages of the UI.	https://registry.diamas.org/registry
Register an organisation: This page details the organisation registration and updating process.	https://registry.diamas.org/register
Forum: This page presents the EDCH Forum, and guides users through the registration process on the platform.	https://registry.diamas.org/forum
Organisations: This page serves as the main public directory for organisations listed in the EDCH Registry. It consists of two elements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sidebar: This panel features faceted filters enabling users to search by "Organisation Name," "Country," "Organisation Type," and "Services offered or supported." ● Main content: This area displays a list of registered organisations, each presented in a card-like format that includes their basic profile details. 	https://registry.diamas.org/organisations-view
Map: This interactive map displays the locations of registered organisations within the EDCH Registry.	https://registry.diamas.org/organisations-map
Glossary: This section contains definitions of key concepts and descriptions of the services offered by registered organisations.	https://registry.diamas.org/glossary

FAQ: This section lists and provides short answers to Frequently Asked Questions	https://registry.diamas.org/frequently-asked-questions
Documentation: This section details the components of organisational profiles in the Registry.	https://registry.diamas.org/documentation
Log in; Create an account: Active elements that redirect users to the account creation/login form.	
Terms of Use, Cookies Notice: These are standard informational sections providing essential background and legal details.	https://registry.diamas.org/terms-use-and-policies

Table 2. Main sections of the Registry's public User Interface.

The website content is organised as follows:

- About
- Registry
 - Map
 - Glossary
- Register an organisation
 - Documentation
 - FAQ
- Forum

Image 1. Part of the Registry main web page.

4. The EDCH Forum

4.1 Selection of platform

The Forum (<https://forum.diamas.org/>) has been deployed on an instance of the Discourse platform, an out-of-the-box solution that enables the creation of online communities. Discourse was selected following a review of available solutions, including both community-owned and proprietary services, and considering aspects such as ease of use, sustainability, features, and long-term maintenance. Discourse was chosen because it is an open-source platform and a track record of adoption across diverse communities. Additionally, the Provider offers hosting and platform management plans, which ensure technical stability.

Its key functionalities address the project's scope to provide a venue that will foster the interaction between individual members of the IPSP/IPTP network. Discourse supports features such as real-time posting, notifications, responsiveness, gamification workflows, which enhance user experience and allow for the creation of customisable content.

Additionally, the platform includes several technical features that facilitate effective moderation, such as tools for managing content and users, flagging, automated spam detection, and user trust levels. These allow administrators to monitor usage as well as to maintain control over shared posts and user communities. Its built-in interoperability mechanisms can integrate with various web services and other installations via APIs and plugins that support user single sign-on (SSO) and data synchronisation with external systems.

A full-year subscription to the Discourse Business plan was initiated in December 2024. This plan includes a range of features designed to support the establishment of the Forum as an independent communication venue, enable effective moderation by the administrative team, and facilitate the growth of its user community. Subscription renewal costs will be covered by the EDCH operational budget.

4.2 User and content management

4.2.1 Content structuring

Discussions on the Forum are organised into **Categories**. A **Topic** is a collection of related messages subsequently posted under a specific title, within a category. Each individual message on a topic is called a **Post**. This classification schema results in a

hierarchical presentation of posted content, helping users navigate through different categories and topics, and engage in discussions relevant to their interests. **Tags** are also used to label discussions on a specific topic, both within and across overarching categories.

The main categories used in the EDCH Forum correspond to the core components of the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS):

1. Funding
2. Legal ownership, mission, and governance
3. Open science practices
4. Editorial management, quality, and research integrity
5. Publishing infrastructure, interoperability, and collaboration
6. Visibility, communication, marketing, and impact
7. Equity, diversity, inclusion, and multilingualism

Two additional categories have been introduced to facilitate moderation and user interaction:

8. General: news, events, newcomer introductions, and general discussions
9. Feedback: discussion about the Forum and its organisation, suggestions for improvement

The following categories have been created to support the DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA consortia, and are accessible only to designated users:

10. Registry: used by the Registry administrators to review submitted profiles
11. Diamond Discovery Hub (DDH): used by the DDH administrators to discuss verification of submitted metadata
12. National Capacity Centres: supports the coordination and interaction of the European network of National Capacity Centres (NCC)

4.2.2 User registration

Posted content is visible to all visitors. However, users must sign up to participate in a discussion. An individual can join the EDCH Forum under one of the following two conditions:

1. They are affiliated with an organisation listed in the Registry, or
2. They are involved in any capacity in the European Diamond OA landscape.

The user's affiliation with an organisation is validated during the registration process, during which they are asked to provide the name of their organisation and a link to its

profile in the Registry. In the latter case, the individual is requested to provide a brief statement about their involvement in a Diamond OA-related initiative.

The registration process consists of three main steps: creating an account, verifying it, and completing a final review by platform administrators or moderators. This final step ensures that participants meet the eligibility criteria and helps maintain a secure, constructive community.

4.2.3 User roles and permissions

User permissions are defined on the basis of the “User trust level” system in the Discourse platform.⁴ This is a built-in feature that grants more permissions as users become more active. There are five trust levels (0–4), which are automatically assigned based on user activity (e.g. total reading time, replies, reactions to posted content).

Upon approval, users enter the Forum under “User Trust Level 1”, and they are allowed to use all core Discourse functions, including image uploading, posting and post flagging, and private messaging. The Trust Level can be upgraded, as users interact with content and the Forum community. Moderators and administrators hold special privileges and responsibilities within the platform, and are manually assigned by the platform management team. The table outlines user roles and corresponding rights:

Role description	Permissions/ Rights
Regular user: Authenticated user with basic rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reads, posts, and reacts to messages - Edits their own posts - Reports inappropriate content - Earns trust based on activity
Moderator: Oversees discussions and ensures community guidelines are followed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Actively participates in discussions and engage users - Moderates posts (edit, delete, move), merge topics - Handles reports - Suspends or bans users
Staff member: General term covering both administrators and moderators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accesses internal moderation tools - Views staff-only messages - Participates in forum management activities
Administrator: Responsible for overall	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Full access to all site features

⁴ <https://blog.discourse.org/2018/06/understanding-discourse-trust-levels/>

configuration and management of the platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Manages users and groups - Installs plugins and themes - Performs backups and restores
--	--

Table 3. User roles and permissions

4.3 Forum moderation

Selection of moderators

Moderators are selected based on their involvement in developing specific elements of DOAS. This ensures that they are familiar with the context and the content of the Forum; they are not necessarily subject matter experts, but serve primarily as facilitators of constructive discussions. As of 11 June 2025, eight moderators have been appointed, representing multiple institutional, geographic, and linguistic backgrounds.

The Forum welcomes volunteers who wish to support topic moderation. Expressions of interest are handled by the administrators and evaluated considering the volunteers' previous engagement on the Forum.

Terms of involvement

Moderation is a flexible and time-limited commitment. Moderators participate on a voluntary basis and may adjust their involvement depending on availability and interest. This approach supports sustainable engagement and reduces the burden on individual contributors.

Daily activities and engagement

Moderators play a key role in shaping a welcoming, inclusive, and constructive community. Thus, they are encouraged to be proactive and remain visible within the community. Their role goes beyond upholding the community guidelines and includes:

- Initiating and guiding discussions within their areas of interest
- Engaging constructively with users to support knowledge exchange
- Maintaining respectful and inclusive dialogue across topics

Moderation tools

Discourse offers a range of tools to support effective moderation. These include:

- Account approval: moderators verify that new users either belong to an organisation listed in the EDCH Registry or are involved in European Diamond OA initiatives
- Content management: posts can be edited for clarity, and topics can be moved to more appropriate categories when needed

[D4.5 IPSP Registry]

- User communication: Moderators may send direct messages to welcome new members, request clarifications, or address minor issues
- Handling users' reports: reports and flags are reviewed, with escalation to the administrators as appropriate
 - De-escalation tools: moderators can pause topics, enable slow mode, or issue official warnings if discussions become unproductive or heated

All significant moderation actions are documented in internal logs to ensure transparency.

Internal coordination

To ensure consistency and shared understanding, moderators work in close coordination with the administrators. Communication mechanisms include:

- Staff Category: a private section dedicated to discussing moderation actions, policies, and user concerns
- Staff Channel: a dedicated group conversation space for real-time interaction between moderators and administrators
- Regular meetings to share feedback, identify challenges, and adjust moderation practices

The detailed instructions for moderators are presented in the annexed informational texts (Annex 3).

5. Dissemination and Engagement

The project has implemented a comprehensive, multi-layered dissemination and community engagement strategy. Its primary objective has been to structure and expand the IPSP/IPTP network as well as an active community of individuals engaged in Diamond OA initiatives. A set of targeted messages has been developed to highlight the benefits of an organisation's inclusion in the Registry and to encourage affiliated individuals to actively participate in Forum discussions.

One of the main challenges in the dissemination and engagement efforts has been to clearly communicate the distinct –yet complementary– scope of the two components. As a result, the key message of the dissemination campaign has been: *“The Registry is for organisations, the Forum is for people.”*

This dual focus required tailored messaging, targeted outreach strategies, and the creation of the following supporting documentation and communication tools:

- **Communication brief:** An advocacy document designed for intermediaries such as Capacity Centres, and partners of the DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA projects. It provides guidance on how to effectively promote the Registry and Forum, with clear messaging, defined audiences, and outlined benefits of community participation.
- **Step-by-Step toolkit:** Developed as part of the “Toolkit for IPTP/IPSP network” (Pauhlac et al., forthcoming), the “EDCH presentation toolkit”⁵ presents the main services that the EDCH offers and highlights their relevance to the Diamond OA community.
- **Multimedia resources:** Two explanatory videos have been produced to support the onboarding of organisations in the Registry, and guide users through the workflows to create and update organisational profiles.⁶ To ensure wider accessibility, English subtitles have been added to the videos.

Part of the material was also translated into French, for targeted regional use. Additionally, the email and social media campaigns were adapted to the differentiated target audiences, as described in the next section.

⁵ https://diamas.org/sites/default/files/2025-06/EDCH_Step%20by%20step%20kit.pdf

⁶ “Register an organisation”: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UaL5yGiZA6Q>

“Update an organisation”: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9NvX9-7jqOY>

5.1 Email campaigns and dissemination in existing networks

The engagement strategy includes targeted mass email campaigns leveraging existing networks within the European Research Area (ERA).

The DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA consortia were informed about the soft launch of the platforms and were asked to contribute to the planned dissemination activities. For this purpose, email invitations were created and shared with project partners, with a request to forward them to mailing lists they manage or are part of. This approach facilitated multilingual outreach and ensured broad geographical representation of organisations in the Registry.

The public communication campaign initiated on 6 May 2025, included posts on partners' websites and newsletters.⁷ National Capacity Centres were also involved to reach regional communities. Indicatively, an email campaign launched by the Capacity Centre in Serbia resulted in the submission of more than 30 organisational profiles to the Registry.

Continuous engagement activities will be carried out until the end of the project, and will be sustained by the EDCH Community Task Force (see section 6). As a next step, email invitations will also be forwarded to more than 300 organisations that responded to the survey that the project conducted at an earlier phase (Agnoloni et al., 2023) and provided consent to be contacted about project activities.

5.2 Social media presence

Recognising the role of social media as a vector for rapid dissemination and community building, the EDCH initiated a dedicated social media campaign to coincide with the public launch of the Registry and the Forum.

More specifically, EDCH accounts on LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/eudch/>) and Bluesky (<https://bsky.app/profile/eudch.bsky.social>) were created shortly before the release of the two platforms. The initial post announcing the Registry and Forum on LinkedIn

⁷ "Actively get involved in the newly evolving European Diamond OA ecosystem:

Join the European Diamond Capacity Hub Registry and Forum". [SparcEurope newsletter 4/2025](#)

"Join the conversation on sustaining Diamond OA". [SparcEurope newsletter 5/2025](#).

"Join the Registry of the European Diamond Capacity Hub!". [LIBER Insider May 2025](#).

"What's new in the European Diamond Capacity Hub". EIFL website (6 June 2025). <https://www.eifl.net/news/whats-new-european-diamond-capacity-hub>

"The EDCH Registry and Forum are now live". [OPERAS newsletter 2/2025](#).

received 28 likes, 7 reshares, and 795 impressions, resulting in an engagement rate of 8.1%. This figure significantly exceeds standard LinkedIn benchmarks for institutional pages (typically ranging between 2–5%), suggesting high relevance and interest among the audience. A simultaneous post on Bluesky (Figure 1) received more modest engagement (4 likes, 2 reposts), reflecting the platform’s niche audience, and the early stage of the EDCH’s presence.

Figure 1: Introducing the Registry & Forum on LinkedIn and Bluesky (12 May 2025)

To foster continuous engagement, the “EDCH Voices” theme was introduced as a recurring social media feature to spotlight active or noteworthy conversations on the Forum. The first instalment (Figure 2) achieved on LinkedIn 692 impressions, 13 reactions, and 4 reshares, with an engagement rate of 3.9%. As a targeted theme, “EDCH Voices” increases visibility and serves as a monitoring tool that helps identify discussion themes that generate higher engagement, thus informing the future content strategy.

European Diamond Capacity Hub
310 abonnés
1 sem. · 🌐

Voices from our EDCH community: How can we increase recognition of Diamond Open Access?

One of our community members recently raised this important question on the forum:

"I wonder how to increase recognition of Diamond Open Access in my country. Perhaps I need to start some bottom-up initiative before any kind of political support arises. But I guess I need some tools or tips for that. Could you share some ideas that worked in your country? Maybe even some documents or analysis showing the impact of national support for Diamond publishing?"

Here's what others contributed:

- 👉 In Lithuania, it's less about the publishing model and more about visibility: journals indexed in Scopus or Clarivate, and recognized for their quality by the national research council. Some Diamond OA journals there are even ranked Q1 and outperform APC-based journals.
- 👉 In France, we're focusing on strong advocacy: ensuring indexing, engaging policy makers, and leveraging international momentum — like the Diamond Action Plan and the EDCH — to gain national traction. It's a slow but steady process.

These insights highlight the diversity of paths and the importance of context, tools, and persistent advocacy.

Add your voice: <https://lnkd.in/e4UaiC5U>

#DiamondOA #OpenAccess #ScholarlyPublishing #Advocacy #AcademicCom

Afficher la traduction

How to increase recognition of Diamond Open Access
forum.diamas.org

European Diamond Capacity Hub
@eudch.bsky.social

Voices from the #EDCHForum:
"How can we raise recognition for #DiamondOA? I'm thinking of starting a bottom-up initiative, but I need tools or examples..."
From Lithuania to France, the answers are insightful: #indexing, #advocacy, international leverage.
👉 Add your voice: buff.ly/feFWqKe

How to increase recognition of Diamond Open Access
I wonder how to increase recognition of Diamond Open Access in my country (Czech Republic). Perhaps I need to start some bottom up initiative before any kind of politic...
© buff.ly

23 mai 2025 à 10:01 🌐 Tout le monde peut répondre 🗨️ · Traduire

1 repost 2 ont aimé

Figure 2: Initial "EDCH Voices" highlight on LinkedIn and Bluesky (23 May 2025)

5.3 Participation in public events

The presentation of the Registry and the Forum in conferences and networking events is an integral part of the engagement strategy, as these venues provide opportunities to increase visibility, collect feedback, and support stakeholder onboarding. The two platforms have already been presented at:

1. The EASE (European Association of Science Editors) Conference, in Oslo. Poster title: *European Diamond Capacity Hub: Supporting Integrity and Equity in Diamond Open Access Publishing*⁸
2. The annual meeting of AEUP (Association of European University Presses), in Vienna, as part of a keynote speech focused on the sustainability of institutional publishing.⁹
3. The final DIAMAS conference, as one of the core services that the EDCH offers to the Diamond OA community.¹⁰

⁸ <https://zenodo.org/records/15526130>

⁹ AEUP Conference agenda: <https://www.aeup.eu/conferences/2025-4th-aeup-conference/>

¹⁰ DIAMAS conference agenda: <https://diamasproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/06/Programme-of-the-DIAMAS-Final-conference3.pdf>

The following submissions to upcoming conferences and networking events have been accepted:

1. CRAFT-OA Summer School
Presentation title: *Beyond CRAFT-OA: The European Diamond Capacity Hub*¹¹
2. Meetings of two French national Open Science working groups
Presentation title: *European Diamond Capacity Hub: Pour une édition en accès ouvert diamant en Europe*
3. The Open Science Fair, 2025
Title: *The European Diamond Capacity Hub: Empowering the Diamond OA Community* (demo session of the EDCH services)

5.4 Webinars

To ensure accessibility across linguistic and geographical boundaries, a series of webinars in English and other languages have been planned until the end of the project. An initial webinar¹² is scheduled for 9 July 2025, with a live demonstration of the platforms' functionalities and features, and testimonials by community users. The webinar also aims to collect feedback and suggestions for improvement through a Q&A session.

This webinar is designed to serve as a reusable template, enabling Capacity Centres and consortium partners to replicate the format in their respective languages and regions. This modular approach addresses potential language barriers and enhances localised engagement, to address inclusivity and maximise community input.

5.5 Engagement overview

5.5.1 Forum (April–June 2025)

Since its soft launch in April and public release on 6 May 2025, the Forum has shown encouraging levels of engagement and activity. Between 10 March and 9 June 2025, the platform recorded 96 user registrations, 44 new topics, and 115 posts. The official launch marked a clear turning point, with a notable increase in pageviews and participation,

¹¹ CRAFT-OA Summer School Programme: <https://www.craft-oa.eu/2nd-craft-oa-summer-school-programme/>

¹² Connect with the European Diamond OA Community: The Forum & Registry of the European Diamond Capacity Hub (webinar presentation): <https://forum.diamas.org/t/discover-the-edch-forum-registry-two-services-to-connect-with-the-european-diamond-oa-community-webinar/313>

particularly during the weeks of 6 and 13 May, when the highest levels of logged-in user activity were recorded.

Engagement has remained steady, with an average of 3 daily engaged users, a DAU/MAU ratio (Daily Active Users (DAU) to Monthly Active Users (MAU)) of 21%, and 20 new contributors actively joining discussions (Figure 3). As of 25 June 2025, the forum counts 129 members, reflecting a growing interest in this space for collaboration and exchange within the Diamond Open Access community.

Figure 3: Forum engagement (April - June 25th)

5.5.2 Registry (April-June 2025)

Web Traffic analytics for the Registry will be handled through Matomo, an open-source web analytics platform. Metrics will include visits, page views, user interactions, and navigation paths. This information will help understand how the Registry is accessed and used.

The table presents the geographical distribution of registered organisations, as of 25 June 2025:

Country	Number of organisations
Belgium	1
Croatia	2
Czechia	1
Denmark	1
Egypt	1 (French organisation)
France	14
Germany	13
Greece	1
Ireland	1
Italy	5
Lithuania	4
Netherlands	4
North Macedonia	1
Norway	1
Poland	1
Portugal	3
Serbia	22
Slovenia	1
Spain	4
Switzerland	2
Tunisia	2
United Kingdom	15
TOTAL	100

Table 4. EDCH Registry: Membership and country allocation

The project will continue to build on these differentiated strategies, informed by user feedback and platform analytics, to strengthen adoption and active participation across the European Diamond Open Access ecosystem.

6. Further developments and sustainability

The sustainability of the Registry and the Forum is secured through their integration into the EDCH. The EDCH is supported by a consortium of institutions and six specialised Task Forces, whose coordinating organisations are responsible for sustaining the EDCH components and further developing the Hub's services to the Diamond OA community.¹³

As building blocks of the IPSP/IPTP network, the Registry and the Forum are managed by the Community Task Force, coordinated by OPERAS. This Task Force aims to establish a community of practice around Diamond OA publishing and to streamline operations for greater efficiency and impact. It brings together partners from the DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA consortia, along with representatives from Capacity Centres, IPSPs, and IPTPs, who work collectively to engage users and organisations in the activities of the network.

Administrators of the Registry and the Forum are selected from within the Task Force. To stimulate community involvement and ensure its active participation in promoting and managing the Registry and the Forum, a call for advocates has been launched.¹⁴ In parallel, a long-term collaboration framework is being developed with National Capacity Centres (NCCs) that support Diamond OA, to ensure the sustainability of the IPSP/IPTP network and outline future activities.

The Community Task Force, together with the NCCs will coordinate and implement key activities such as regular calls to update organisational profiles in the Registry; webinars and engagement events at national and regional level; and moderating discussions on the Forum. Platform administrators will monitor overall usage and report regularly to the Task Force, which will be responsible for implementing measures to enhance uptake and stimulate engagement if needed.

¹³ A detailed overview of the EDCH Task Forces is provided on the EDCH main website (<https://diamas.org/task-forces>)

¹⁴ <https://forum.diamas.org/t/join-the-movement-the-edch-is-looking-for-its-advocates/331>

7. Conclusion

The EDCH Registry and Forum are interconnected building components of the IPSP/IPTP network; they serve as virtual spaces designed to foster collaboration, networking, and knowledge exchange among institutions and individuals engaged in Diamond OA across Europe.

The EDCH Registry and Forum operate in a complementary manner, and form one of the Hub's core services: the Registry serves as the primary entry point to the network, while the Forum provides a dynamic venue where community members can exchange information and collaboratively address challenges.

In their initial months of operation, the Registry and the Forum have benefited from a robust, multi-channel communication and engagement strategy that combined centralised coordination with decentralised outreach through local networks. This resulted in an encouraging uptake of the platforms over the first two months since their public launch. To ensure their continued use, a dedicated EDCH Task Force has been established to bring together operational members of the Hub and representatives from the community. Working collaboratively, this Task Force will focus on the operational sustainability and future expansion of the network.

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Annex 1: Registry Website Contents

1. Main page <https://registry.diamas.org/>

[Title] **Register. Connect. Grow.**

The EDCH Registry and Forum are designed **to foster collaboration and networking** among Diamond Open Access **Publishers, Service Providers,** and **Tools and Technology Providers** in Europe.

Buttons: Explore (directs to <https://registry.diamas.org/organisations>)
Register (directs to <https://registry.diamas.org/register>)

[Title] **Your gateway to the Diamond OA community**

Increase Visibility: **Register, present and promote** your organisation's profile, highlighting its expertise, services, and operational capacities.

Find the Right Partners; **Discover** Publishers, Service Providers, Tools and Technology Providers, and **identify** potential partners to collaborate with.

Button: Read more (directs to <https://registry.diamas.org/registry>)

Join a Collaborative Network: **Access** the ECDH Forum, a **collaborative, dynamic and inclusive space** to exchange knowledge, share best practices, and strengthen partnerships.

[Title] **The Registry is for organisations. The Forum is for people.**

Join the discussion

Members of registered organisations or individuals involved in the European Diamond OA landscape can join the forum and engage with the Diamond OA community, share insights, and collaborate on key challenges.

Button: Visit the Forum (directs to <https://registry.diamas.org/forum>)

[Title] **How to register?**

[Browse](#) the profiles of registered organisations, discover their services and expertise for potential collaborations, and search for your own organisation.

Can't find your organisation, or need to update its profile? Just follow these steps!

1. **First time here? Sign in!** Create an account to get started.

2. **Updating an existing organisation?** Request management rights and wait for approval.
Registering a new organisation? Move on to Step 3!
3. **Complete your organisation's registration.** Fill out or update the registration form and submit it. Once we review it based on our criteria, you're good to go!

[Title] **How to join the Forum?**

1. **New to the Forum?** Sign in now and create your account by providing your name, username, email address, password, and organisation name (if registered).
2. **Stay tuned – Your access is on the way!** Wait for the administrators to approve your request. Once approved, you'll receive a confirmation email granting you full access.
3. **Ready to go!** Engage with the community, start conversations, share insights, and exchange ideas with other members!

[Title] **Still have questions? Need more clarity?**

Check out our [FAQ](#), and if you need further assistance, feel free to contact us at [registry\[at\]diamas.org](mailto:registry@diamas.org)

2. About <https://registry.diamas.org/registry>

[Title] **What is the Registry?**

The Registry of the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH) is more than just a directory—it's a dynamic, free and comprehensive resource designed to **foster collaborations** within the Diamond Open Access (OA) landscape in the European Research Area.

It offers a platform where **Publishers, Service Providers, and Tools and Technology Providers** can **register, present, and promote** their profiles, enhancing their **visibility** and showcasing their **expertise and operational capacities** in Diamond OA publishing.

[Title] **Why join the Registry?**

The primary objective of the Registry is to document and provide comprehensive, up-to-date information on organisations involved in Diamond OA publishing within the European Research Area. By registering your organisation, you become part of a vibrant and growing network working to advance Diamond OA publishing.

The Registry helps you to:

- Promote your organisation, and gain recognition for its role in shaping the future of OA publishing
- Discover tailored technologies and services designed to address your needs
- Stay up-to-date with the latest developments, best practices, and discover opportunities for collaboration

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- Find partners—from institutional publishers to infrastructure providers
- Strengthen your OA strategy by learning from peers and established operational models

By participating, you contribute to a **stronger, more connected Diamond OA landscape** where collaboration drives innovation, and collective action shapes the future of Diamond OA publishing.

[Title] **How to use the Registry?**

Explore the Registry in different ways:

- [Browse or search](#) for Diamond Publishers, Service Providers, or Tools and Technology Providers.
- [Explore the interactive map](#) to find organisations across the European Research Area.

Want to be part of the Registry? [Check out how to register and join the network!](#) (redirects to Register)

3. Registry <https://registry.diamas.org/organisations-view>

[Link redirects to the list of registered organisations]

3.1 Glossary <https://registry.diamas.org/glossary>

This section is designed to help you understand key concepts and the range of services offered by registered organisations. Use this guide to familiarise with important terminology and gain a clear overview of the information presented in the organisational profiles.

Glossary of terms

Academic books: A long-form scholarly publication, including monographs, book chapters, edited collections, critical editions, and other long-form scholarly works. Often the result of in-depth academic research making an original contribution to a field of study.

Academic/Scholarly Journals: A serial or periodical publication, with an ISSN in which scholarship relating to either particular academic disciplines or multidisciplinary research is published.

Conference output: This category includes all conference output, with the exception of conference proceedings published with ISSNs (see Academic/Scholarly journal articles above).

Grey literature: Defined as “[t]hat which is produced on all levels of government, academics, business and industry in print and electronic formats, but which is not controlled by commercial publishers” by the Fourth International Conference on Grey Literature (Grey Literature Database, 1999. ‘What Is Grey Literature?’). We use it here to define outputs produced outside of traditional publishing and distribution channels described above.

Institution: A not-for-profit academic or scholarly organisation. These include but are not limited to research performing organisations (RPOs), Research funding organisations (RFOs),

organisations connected to RPOs (university libraries, university presses, faculties, and departments), research institutes, scholarly societies.

Publisher: Organisations responsible for preparing, producing, and distributing scholarly content to the public. This content can take various forms, such as books, journals, and conference proceedings.

Service Provider: Any entity that provides services and/or infrastructure to authors and publishers for scholarly publishing. These services may be provided by the publisher itself (in which case the publisher is also the service provider) or by other entities inside or outside the institution. Such activities include, but are not limited to: (a) editorial activities (selection of manuscripts, peer-review, etc.); (b) operational activities (production activities like copy editing, proofreading, type-setting, creating metadata), IT activities, communication activities (marketing/dissemination, social media, etc), as well as administrative and financial activities (contracts, accounting, documentation, etc.).

Tools & Technology Provider: Any entity that provides tools and/or technologies such as standards, code, hardware and software that enable any user and service provider to perform specific tasks or operations to achieve their objectives. Such tools and technologies include, but are not limited to, publishing software, format converters, XML and content structuration standards, peer review management systems, editing tools, PIDs, data exchange protocols.

Non-academic outputs: Includes research outputs intended to reach a broader audience beyond academia, such as project information/communication, articles in a newspaper or magazine, interviews and press releases.

Other research outputs and output formats: Includes textual and non-textual research outputs such as Creative writing, Artwork, Sound and video recordings, Exhibition catalogues, Musical score or notation, Datasets, Software, Digital Scholarship, Intellectual Property, Patents/Trademarks Digital or Visual Products, Artefact, Exhibition, Performance, Composition, Design, Devices and Products, and Portfolio works.

Glossary of Services

Content format production: the action of giving a stable form to the published content.

Copy editing/language editing/proofreading: various actions performed on text content.

Displaying/Disseminating: the action of publicising content via specific software or platforms.

Editorial decisions/Peer review management: the actions related to handling manuscripts and correspondence with authors.

Hosting: the action of controlling the material space on which published content appears.

Identification: the action of attributing permanent identifiers to content, mostly text, authors and data.

Income management: the action of applying for, contracting, paying, and accounting monetary resources.

Indexing: the action of putting data on outputs as books, book series, journals in commercial or open databases like Scopus, DOAB/DOAJ or WoS.

Intellectual property rights and licensing: actions related to the acquisition, the transfer of content property, and the scope of its uses.

Marketing: the actions relating to funding streams to support the Publisher or its partners, enhancing audiences, and increasing content outreach.

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Metadata production: the action of linking any useful data to content often by software, on the basis of information provided by authors at the time of submission.

Preservation: the action of archiving and preserving content in the long term.

Printing: any action related to the production, selling and dissemination of printed material.

Training: different sets of actions performed by Publishers to improve the skills of their teams or those of associated stakeholders, including editors and authors.

3.2 Map

[Link redirects to the interactive map]

4. Register an organisation (<https://registry.diamas.org/register>)

[Title] **Who is invited to register?**

1. Publishers: Organisations responsible for preparing, producing, and distributing scholarly content to the public, such as books, journals, conference proceedings, and other research outputs and formats.

2. Service Providers: Entities providing infrastructure and support for scholarly publishing—from editorial and production to IT, marketing, finance, and beyond.

3. Tools and Technology Providers: Providers of software, standards, and tech solutions that power scholarly publishing—such as peer review systems, XML structuring tools, metadata standards, PIDs, and content management platforms.

Before registering, please [check](#) if your organisation is already included in the Registry.

[Title] **What are our criteria for inclusion?**

To be listed, an organisation must meet the following criteria:

- Active in the Diamond OA ecosystem: operate as a Publisher, Service Provider, or Tools and Technology Provider supporting Diamond OA publishing.
- Commitment to community ownership: demonstrate governance by and for the community, including researchers and scholars.
- Be a public legal entity: have a defined legal status (non-profit, academic institution, government entity, or for-profit with Diamond OA support) to ensure transparency.
- Be part of the European landscape: must be either located in – or have a parent organisation located in – a country that is part of the [European Research Area](#) (ERA) or an observer to the [European Research Area and Innovation Committee](#) (ERAC).

Important notes:

- For-profit entities can only qualify as Service Providers, if they directly support Diamond OA.
- Individual journals are not eligible—the Registry hosts organisations enabling Diamond OA publishing.

Check [here](#) for more details on the criteria for inclusion and their relevance to the principles of Diamond OA. Redirects to <https://registry.diamas.org/criteria-inclusion-registry>

[Title] **How to register an organisation?**

You can submit or update your organisation’s profile information through a simple process. Follow these steps:

[Title] **Can’t find your organisation?**

Step 1: Create an account

To create an account, you need to provide the following information:

- A valid **institutional** email address.
- The name of the organisation you are affiliated with.
- Your position or role within the organisation.

Once you submit the registration form, you will receive an email to verify your account before proceeding to the next step.

Step 2: Complete your organisation’s profile

Fill out additional details about your organisation and its services.

Information required:

- Identification information (e.g. name; country; website)
- Services provided and supported outputs
- Main contacts

✦ For reference, please check the documentation [here](#).

Step 3: Review & validation

Once you have submitted the registration form, our team will review your organisation’s profile.

- If all details are complete, you will receive a confirmation email, and the organisation’s profile will be published.
- If changes are required, our team will contact you for the necessary updates.

Please allow some time for the review process. You will be notified as soon as a decision is made!

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[Title] **Do you want to update your organisation's information?**

If your organisation is already in the Registry but its profile is outdated, you can initiate an update.

Step 1: Sign in or create an account

If you are already managing the organisation, sign in to access the organisation's profile and go to step 3!

To create an account, you need to provide the following information:

- Email Address: a valid institutional email address.
- The name of the organisation you are affiliated with.
- Your position or role within the organisation.

Once you submit the registration form, you will receive an email to verify your account before proceeding to the next step.

Step 2: Request management rights & wait for approval

Once your account is created, you will see a list of matching organisations, based on the information you provided.

1. Select your organisation from the list.
2. Submit a request to manage the profile.
3. Our admin team or the current owner of the profile will review your request and validate your access.

Step 3: Update your organisation's profile

When you are granted management rights, you will be able to access your organisation's profile. If you need to update your organisation's details, simply modify the information you wish to change and submit the registration form.

Wait for approval from our admin team. You will be notified once the public profile is updated!

If your organisation is already registered and you don't need to update its profile, join the forum!

Before you [register your organisation](#), please consult the [FAQ](#) and relevant [documentation](#).

Button: Register (<https://registry.diamas.org/login-register>)

4.1 Documentation <https://registry.diamas.org/documentation>

This section details the components of organisational profiles in the Registry. When registering an organisation, you will be prompted to complete the relevant fields. Definitions of the terms used in the profiles can be found in the Registry [glossary](#).

Comprehensive details about the profile elements, and instructions for completing the registration form are also available in a downloadable document.

When registering an organisation, you will be asked to enter **the contact information of the person(s) responsible for the management of the organisation's profile in the Registry**. The contact person(s) will be receiving updates from the Registry in the designated email addresses. The contact details of the contact persons will not be published on the Registry.

The following details will be required during the registration process:

1. Name (mandatory): The official name of the Publisher / Provider in the original language and its commonly used English name or acronym (if any).

2. Website (mandatory): The URL of the main page of the department or unit of the Publisher / Provider that publishes material or provides services and/or tools.

3. Service contact (mandatory): The official contact email address of the organisation. This email address will be used for inquiries or collaboration requests from other organisations and will be stored in the Registry database.

4. Type (mandatory): The type that the organisation identifies with (Publisher; Service Provider; Tools and Technology Provider).

5. Country (mandatory): The country and the city (optionally) where the main address of the Publisher / Provider is located.

6. Supported languages (mandatory): The language/s in which publications are available and/or services and tools are provided.

7. Parent organisation (mandatory): The name of the Publisher / Provider's parent organisation (if any).

8. Legal entity type (mandatory): The type of legal entity of the Publisher / Provider or its parent organisation (e.g. public organisation, not-for-profit, company, corporation, or other).

9. Number of Full-Time Equivalent (FTE) paid staff (optional): Number of paid staff directly employed, or contracted, or seconded in the department or unit that publishes material or provides services and/or tools (i.e., editorial, production and operational staff in Full-Time Equivalent [FTE]).

10. Services and tools offered (mandatory): The kind of services that the Publisher / Provider offers.

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11. Geographical range of services (optional): The geographical scope of the services offered by the Publisher / Provider (national, regional, international).

12. Links to tools and services (optional) :The URLs where the services are described and/or the tools are available for purchase/download.

13. Published or supported output types (mandatory): The output types that the organisation publishes or provides services and tools for.

14. Disciplinary coverage (mandatory): The discipline(s) that the Publisher / Provider mainly covers.

15. Other Registries in which the Publisher / Provider is included (optional)

16. Funding opportunities (optional): Whether the organisation is looking for funding opportunities to support its Diamond OA activities.

Additionally, upon completing the registration, you will be asked to confirm that a) all information provided is accurate; b) the person who provided the information is an authorised representative of the organisation; c) with the exception of the details and email addresses of the main and secondary contact persons, all information can be accessible via the Registry.

4.2 FAQ <https://registry.diamas.org/frequently-asked-questions>

What type of information is published on the Registry?

The EDCH Registry displays profiles of organisations in a clear and accessible format. The elements of the profiles include:

- Organisation name and contact information
- Organisation type and relationship to parent entities (if applicable)
- Services offered and tools/technologies supported
- Geographic range of services
- Types of outputs published or supported
- Supported languages
- Disciplinary focus
- Links to service descriptions and access points

Is my organisation eligible to be included in the Registry?

The Registry welcomes organisations in the European Research Area involved in Diamond OA publishing:

- **Publishers:** organisations responsible for preparing, producing, and distributing scholarly content to the public. This content can take various forms, such as books, journals, and conference proceedings.

- **Service Providers:** organisations that provide services and/or infrastructure to authors, editors and publishers for scholarly publishing. Such activities include, but are not limited to: editorial activities; operational activities (copy editing, proofreading, type-setting, creating metadata); IT activities; communication activities (marketing/dissemination, social media, etc); as well as administrative and financial activities.
- **Tools and Technology Providers:** organisations that provide tools and/or technologies such as standards, code, hardware and software that enable Publishers and service providers to perform specific tasks or operations to achieve their objectives.

Important notes:

- For-profit entities can only qualify as Service Providers if they directly support Diamond OA.
- Journals are not eligible—this registry is for organisations enabling Diamond OA publishing.

Who can register their organisation?

An organisation can be registered by individual users who are authorised as representatives of their respective organisations.

Who can join the forum?

All members of registered organisations or individuals involved in the European Diamond OA landscape can join the forum by creating their own account.

To check if your organisation is already registered, search our database. If it is not listed, register and create its profile. (To access the forum, the editorial team of a journal should check if its publisher is registered, rather than its hosting platform).

How is data collected and updated?

The Registry database was initially populated with data collected by the [DIAMAS](#) project. Individual users, authorised as representatives of their respective organisation, are granted editing rights for the organisation's profile in the Registry. These representatives are responsible for ensuring the accuracy of the data by regularly updating their organisation's profile elements.

5. Forum <https://registry.diamas.org/forum>

[Title] Go further with the EDCH Forum

The European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH) Forum is a collaborative and inclusive space designed for individuals and organisations involved in Diamond Open Access (OA) publishing.

Whether you're part of a registered organisation listed in the EDCH Registry or actively involved in the European Diamond OA landscape, the Forum is for you.

Designed to foster collaboration and knowledge sharing across the Diamond OA community, the Forum serves as a virtual meeting point where participants can engage in meaningful discussions on a range of topics and share solutions and best practices to address the challenges of Diamond OA publishing. It's a space to learn from one another, strengthen community ties, and advance the Diamond model.

The Forum allows members to:

- **Exchange knowledge and best practices** with peers
- Ask questions, receive support, and **tackle challenges together**
- Co-develop solutions, share resources, and **build an engaged community of practice**

[Title] **Where is the Forum hosted?**

The Forum is hosted on [Discourse](#), an open-source platform designed to support online discussions.

[Guidelines](#) and [tips](#) for new users provide an overview of the Forum's main features and instructions on how to get started.

[Title] **Community engagement and trust-levels**

The Forum uses a trust-level system to encourage positive participation: new users gradually unlock additional permissions as they engage. This system helps maintain a welcoming and well-organised space for productive discussions.

[Title] **How to join the Forum**

Joining the EDCH Forum is simple. You can create an account on the Forum if:

- Your organisation is listed in the EDCH Registry, or
 - You are involved in any way in the European Diamond OA landscape.
1. [Check](#) if your organisation is listed in the Registry, or be ready to briefly explain your involvement in Diamond OA when creating your account.
 2. **Sign up:** Create your account in the Forum and activate it via the verification email.
 3. Await approval from a Forum moderator. Once approved, you will receive a confirmation email granting you full access.

6. Criteria for inclusion in the Registry <https://registry.diamas.org/criteria-inclusion-registry>

Be active in the Diamond Open Access publishing ecosystem

Organisations must demonstrate active involvement in the Diamond OA publishing ecosystem in one or more of the following capacities:

- as a Publisher: Responsible for preparing, producing, and distributing Diamond OA scholarly content to the public, including publishing or supporting journals, books, or any publications with no fees for authors or readers.
- as a Service Provider: Entity that provides infrastructure and support for Diamond OA publishing, including but not limited to editorial and production services, IT support, marketing or outreach services, and financial management.
- as a Tools and Technology Provider: Provider of software, standards, and technological solutions that support Diamond OA publishing, such as peer review systems, XML structuring tools, metadata standards, persistent identifiers (PIDs), and content management platforms.

Relevance: These criteria ensure that only Publishers, Service Providers, Tools and Technology Providers genuinely involved in and contributing to the Diamond Open Access publishing ecosystem are included, creating a community committed to equitable access to scholarly content.

Commit to community ownership

Publishers, Service Providers or Tools and Technology Providers must demonstrate a commitment to community ownership. Publishers, in particular, should indicate that they are governed by and for the community, including researchers and scholars.

Relevance: Emphasising community ownership of the Publisher, Service Provider, or Tools and Technology Provider ensures that the publishing process remains accessible, equitable, and aligned with the values of Diamond OA, promoting collaboration and shared responsibility among stakeholders.

Be a public legal entity

Publishers, Service Providers, Tools and Technology Providers must have a defined public legal entity type (e.g., for-profit, non-profit, academic institution, government entity) to ensure transparency and accountability.

Relevance: Understanding the legal status of an Publisher, Service Provider, or Tools and Technology Provider provides insights into its objectives, funding sources, and governance. This is crucial for determining whether the Publisher, Service Provider, or Tools and

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Technology Provider aligns with the principles of Diamond OA, which typically favours non-profit models.

Be part of the European landscape

Publishers, Service Providers, Tools and Technology Providers must be either located in – or have a parent organisation located in – a country that is part of the [European Research Area](#) (ERA) or an observer to the [European Research Area and Innovation Committee](#) (ERAC).

Additional remarks

Please note that for-profit entities that monetise scientific publishing can only qualify as Service Providers if they support Diamond OA publishing.

Please note that journals—whether they are Diamond OA or otherwise—are not eligible for registration. This is a Registry of organisations that qualify as Publishers, Service Providers or Tools and Technology Providers.

Relevance: This maintains the integrity of the Diamond OA Registry by ensuring that only Publishers, Service Providers, or Tools and Technology Providers aligned with its principles are registered.

Annex 2: Organisation registration form

Please provide complete and accurate details about your organisation. Please note that submitted organisational profiles undergo a review process, which typically takes up to 5 working days. Administrators may request clarifications or additional information from the designated contact person(s).

1. Organisation name (free text - mandatory)

Please enter the official name of the Publisher / Provider *in the original language*.

2. Organisation name (EN) (free text - mandatory)

Name of the Publisher / Provider in English. If the original name is already *in English*, please repeat it in this field.

3. Acronym (free text - optional)

4. Website (free text - mandatory)

Please enter the URL of the main page of the department or unit of the Publisher / Provider that publishes material or provides services and/or tools. **The URL field should begin with the protocol (https:// or http://).**

5. Organisation email address (free text - mandatory)

Please enter the official contact email address of the organisation. This email will be used for inquiries or collaboration requests from other organisations and will be stored in the Registry database. The contact information of the person(s) responsible for

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managing the organisation's profile in the Registry will be requested upon completion of the organisation's profile.

6.Type (multiple choice - mandatory)

- **Publisher** (the entity that controls publishing operations)
- **Service Provider** (any entity tasked by an institution or a Publisher with carrying out specific services)
- **Tools and/or Technology Provider** (an entity that provides tools and/or technologies such as standards, code, hardware and software that enable any user and service provider to perform specific tasks or operations to achieve their objectives)

Please select the type that your organisation identifies with.

7.Country (free text - mandatory)

Please enter the country where the main address of the Publisher / Provider is located.

8.City (free text - optional)

Please enter the city where the main address of the Publisher / Provider is located.

9.Supported languages (multiple choice- mandatory)

10. Parent organisation (selection - mandatory)

Yes/ No

[If yes]

Parent organisation official name (free text)

Parent organisation official name (EN) (free text)

Parent organisation acronym (free text)

Please indicate whether the Publisher / Provider has a parent organisation. If yes, please enter its name in the original language and the commonly used English name (if any).

11. Legal entity type (single choice - mandatory)

1. Public organisation (e.g. university, research institute, laboratory, research organisation)
2. Private not-for-profit organisation (e.g. charity, foundation, learned society, association)
3. Company (owned by Directors; limited liability)
4. Company (owned by shareholders)
5. Other (please specify)

Please enter the type of legal entity of the Publisher / Provider or its parent organisation. If selecting 'other' please describe the legal entity type.

12. Number of full-time equivalent (FTE) paid staff (single choice - optional)

1. None
2. <2
3. 2-5
4. 6-10
5. 11-20
6. 21-30
7. More than 30

Please indicate how many paid staff are directly employed, or contracted, or seconded in the department or unit that publishes material or provides services and/or tools (e.g. editorial, production and operational staff in Full-Time Equivalent [FTE]).

13. Services offered or supported with tools and technologies (multiple choice-mandatory)

- **Content format production:** The action of giving a stable form to the published content. It can be performed by the Publisher, left to authors/journals, or outsourced to a service provider.
- **Copyediting/ language editing/ proofreading:** Various actions performed on text content. Production services (copy-editing, proofreading, typesetting, metadata etc).
- **Displaying/ Disseminating:** The action of publicising content via specific software or platforms. IT services (submission system, platform, website, etc).
- **Editorial decisions/Peer review management:** The actions related to handling manuscripts and correspondence with authors. Editorial services (selection of manuscripts, administration of peer-review, etc).
- **Hosting:** The action of controlling the material space on which published content appears. IT services (submission system, platform, website, etc).
- **Identification:** The action of attributing permanent identifiers to content, mostly text, authors and data.
- **Income management:** The action of applying for, contracting, paying, and accounting monetary resources.
- **Indexing:** The action of putting data on outputs as books, book series, journals in commercial or open databases like Scopus, DOAB/DOAJ or WoS.
- **Intellectual property rights and licensing:** Actions related to the acquisition, the transfer of content property, and the scope of its uses.
- **Marketing:** Actions relating to funding streams to support the Publisher or its partners, enhancing audiences, and increasing content outreach. Communication services (marketing/dissemination, social media, etc).
- **Metadata production:** The action of linking any useful data to content often by software, on the basis of information provided by authors.
- **Preservation:** The action of archiving and preserving content in the long term.
- **Printing:** Actions related to the production, selling and dissemination of printed material.
- **Training:** Different sets of actions performed by Publishers to improve the skills of their teams or those of associated stakeholders, including editors and authors. Training, support and/or advice on publishing policies and best practice.
- **Other** (please specify)

14. Geographical range of services provided (single choice - mandatory)

1. Services provided to parent organisation only
2. National
3. Regional
4. International

[If regional] **Regions services are available in** (single choice)

Europe
Africa
Asia
North America
Latin America

[If international] **Countries services are available in** (single choice)

Please note that "geographical range" does not refer to the availability of published outputs. Your answer should indicate whether the Publisher / Provider can provide services to other organisations at the national, regional, or international level.

15. Services URLs (free text- optional)

Please enter the URLs where the services are described and/or the tools are available for purchase/download. The URL should begin with the protocol (https:// or http://).

16. Published or supported output types (multiple choice - mandatory)

- Academic journals
- Academic books
- Conference output
- Grey literature
- Other research outputs (media, digital products)
- Non-academic outputs
- Other output formats (e.g. datasets, digital scholarship, software)
- Preprints
- Other (please specify)

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Please select the output types that the organisation publishes or provides services and tools for.

17. Disciplinary coverage (multiple choice – mandatory)

- Natural sciences
- Engineering and technology
- Medical and Health sciences
- Agricultural sciences
- Social sciences
- Humanities
- Multidisciplinary

[if individual disciplinary areas are selected, user is prompted to indicate specific disciplinary subfields, based on the Frascati manual]

Select the disciplines that the organisation mainly covers.

18. Other registries / directories in which the institution is included (free text – optional)

Research Organisation Registry (ROR)

IFLALibrary Map of the World

Library Publishing Directory

OPERAS Pathfinder

Global Register of Publishers

Other

Please include the URL or the ID of the organisation's profile in other Registries, where applicable.

19. Are you looking for funding opportunities to support your Diamond OA activities?

(single selection- optional)

N/A

Yes

No

20. Is your organisation interested in becoming a Trusted Source for the Diamond Discovery Hub? (single selection- optional)

N/A

Yes

No

Trusted Sources contribute journal metadata to the Diamond Discovery Hub (DDH), which aims to provide an authoritative list of Diamond OA journals in Europe, helping these journals increase their visibility in the academic community and beyond. Diamond OA journals included in the DDH must fulfil the [six operational criteria for Diamond Open Access](#). Trusted Sources must comply with the [DDH Terms of Service](#). A representative from the DDH team will contact you and guide you through the onboarding process.

Main contact person (free text -mandatory)

Name

Organisation email

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Position

Please enter the contact information of the person(s) responsible for the management of the organisation's profile in the Registry. The contact person(s) will be receiving updates from the Registry in the designated email addresses. Please use email address(es) associated with your affiliated institution. If unavailable, you may use a personal email address; in this case, you may be contacted for verification.

Secondary contact person (free text -mandatory)

Name

Organisation email

Position

I certify that (tick box - mandatory)

- a. All information is accurate and up-to-date.*
- b. I am an authorised representative of the organisation.*
- c. With the exception of (i) the details and email addresses of contact persons, and (ii) the information provided regarding funding opportunities, all other information may be published in the Registry.*

Annex 3: Forum informational texts

1. Welcome to the EDCH Forum! <https://forum.diamas.org/t/welcome-to-the-edch-forum/5>

[Title] **What is the EDCH Forum?**

The EDCH Forum is a dynamic, global community space for people involved in Diamond OA Publishing.

Everyone involved in the European Diamond OA landscape is welcome to join. Simply create an account and follow our [Forum Guidelines](#) to help ensure a safe and respectful experience for all.

You might be thinking, “I don’t have anything to contribute.” **But that’s not true!** Every question, experience, and perspective adds value to our community. Whether you want to ask a question, share a resource, or simply engage with ongoing discussions, your participation matters!

The forum is designed for you—shape it, contribute to it, and let it evolve to meet your needs!

[Title] **How the Forum works:**

- **Categories:** The forum is organised into categories, each representing one of the seven components of the **Diamond Open Access Standard**.
- **Topics:** Within each category, you’ll find topics—each introducing an idea and sparking new conversations.
- **Discussions:** Discussions happen through replies, where members share their insights, ask questions, and exchange knowledge.

[Title] **Here are some quick tips to get started:**

- **Take five minutes to chat** with our @discobot (if you haven’t already)! Just send him a message saying “**start tutorial**” to get started. You might find him helpful!
- **Introduce yourself** by adding your picture and information about yourself and your interests to your profile. What is one thing you’d like to be asked about?
- **Get to know the community** by browsing discussions that are already happening here. When you find a post interesting, informative, or entertaining, use the ❤️ to show your appreciation or support!
- **Contribute** by commenting, sharing your own perspective, asking questions, or offering feedback in the discussion.

[Title] **What languages can I post in?**

The primary language of the forum is English, but users can post in many different languages. You are welcome to post in the language you're most comfortable with.

If you would like to create a discussion in another language, please reach out to the admin team. You should provide a moderator for that language group.

If you need help or have a suggestion, feel free to ask in #site-feedback or contact the admins.

2. Our Forum Guidelines

<https://forum.diamas.org/t/our-forum-guidelines/81>

[Title] **Welcome to the European Diamond Capacity Hub Forum**

A virtual, collaborative, dynamic and inclusive space for discussions, helping members **strengthen connections** and **tackle common challenges** in the field of Diamond Open Access publishing. This forum serves as a shared resource where users (individuals, institutions, organisations) can ask questions, share insights, and discuss the latest developments.

The forum is hosted on **Discourse**, which provides useful resources for newcomers. **Please read them** to familiarise yourself with how to navigate and participate effectively:

- [Understanding Discourse for new users](#)
- [Discourse new user tips and tricks](#)

Discussions are organised into categories based on the [DOAS components](#):

1. Funding
2. Legal ownership, mission, and governance
3. Open science practices
4. Editorial management, quality, and research integrity
5. Publishing infrastructure, interoperability, and collaboration
6. Visibility, communication, marketing, and impact
7. Equity, diversity, inclusion, and multilingualism
8. General: news, newcomer introductions, and open discussions
9. Feedback: discussion about this forum, its organisation, how it works, and how it can be improved.

[Title] **Language policy**

Encouraging diversity and multilingualism

The primary language of the forum is English, but we welcome discussions in other languages to foster multilingualism.

If you would like to create a discussion in another language, **please request a dedicated topic from the admin team**. You should propose a moderator for that language group.

[Title] **A space for thoughtful discussion**

Treat this forum like a **public space**—a shared resource for learning, collaboration, and professional discussions. These guidelines are here to help foster a healthy community environment, where everyone feels welcome to participate and contribute to meaningful discussions.

Our aim is to keep this space welcoming, **respectful, and open to diverse perspectives**. These are simply guidelines to ensure that discussions remain constructive and inclusive. We all have a role to play in maintaining this environment.

[Title] **Improve the discussion**

Every conversation matters. Help us make this a great place for discussion by always working to improve the discussion in some way, however small. If you're unsure whether your post adds value, take a moment to reflect before sharing.

You can also enhance the discussion by exploring existing topics—chances are, someone else may already be discussing the same ideas or challenges. This way, you'll find more opportunities to engage with others who share your interests.

To keep the forum organised, please ensure your posts **are made in the appropriate categories**. **Don't cross-post content** across multiple threads, and **avoid posting empty replies or irrelevant content**. **Keep discussions relevant and on-topic** to ensure that everyone can participate in an efficient, meaningful way.

[Title] **Your participation matters**

The tone of this community is shaped by every interaction. Help create an environment where **thoughtful, respectful, and engaging discussions thrive**.

Discourse provides tools to highlight quality contributions: bookmark, replies, edits, watching or tracking topics to be notified of new content. Use these features to enhance your experience and support a positive community culture.

Let's grow our community together!

[Title] **Disagree thoughtfully and respectfully**

It's perfectly natural to disagree, but it's important to remain respectful. If you find yourself at odds with another member, **focus on ideas rather than individuals**. Here are a few things to avoid:

[D4.5 IPSP Registry]

- Personal attacks
- Name-calling
- Responding to tone instead of content
- Knee-jerk contradictions without constructive input

Instead, offer **well-reasoned counter-arguments** that advance the conversation in a productive way.

[Title] **If you see a problem, report it**

Moderators rely on the community to help maintain quality discussions. If you encounter inappropriate behavior, please **report it directly to the moderators of the relevant category by using the forum messaging system** rather than engaging with the issue yourself or flagging it.

Moderators reserve the right to remove content or accounts that violate these guidelines. However, moderators do not pre-approve posts and are not responsible for content posted by users.

[Title] **Be civil and inclusive**

A healthy conversation can easily be disrupted by rudeness. When using this forum, always be polite and respectful to all members.

- **Be civil** – Do not post anything that could be considered offensive, abusive, or hate speech.
- **Keep it appropriate** – Avoid obscene or sexually explicit content.
- **Respect others** – Do not harass, impersonate, or share private information about anyone.
- **Be mindful of cultural differences** – This forum is used by people from around the world, and English may not be everyone's first language.
- **Keep discussions professional** – This forum is intended for professional conversations.
- **Respect the forum** – Do not post spam or engage in disruptive behaviour.

If you're uncertain about the appropriateness of your message, ask yourself: **"Would I be comfortable seeing this post in a public space?"**

[Title] **Post only your own content**

You are not allowed to post any digital content that belongs to someone else without their permission. Additionally, you may not share descriptions, links, or methods for unlawfully obtaining intellectual property (such as software, videos, audio, or images) or for violating any other laws.

[Title] **Powered by the community**

This forum is **run by moderators and you, the community**. If you have feedback or suggestions, open a topic in #site-feedback and let's discuss!

For urgent issues that require moderator intervention, please contact the moderators of the relevant category directly. The moderator will liaise with the admin team to determine the appropriate course of action.

Thank you for making this forum a valuable and welcoming space for all!

And thank you to the [FAIRdata Forum](#) for inspiring us with their principles and fostering a collaborative and respectful environment that we strive to emulate here.

3. Say it your way: Supporting discussions in all languages

<https://forum.diamas.org/t/say-it-your-way-supporting-discussions-in-all-languages/128>

[Title] **Hello everyone!**

Our community brings together people from across Europe, and with that, a rich mix of languages and cultures. While English is our main language here, we encourage discussions in other languages as well. **Multilingualism is a strength**, and we want this forum to reflect that!

Want to start a conversation in another language?

Great! Here's what to do:

1. Send a quick message to the moderators or admin team to request a dedicated topic for your language.
2. Propose a moderator who can help oversee conversations in that language. This ensures the discussion remains active, respectful, and in line with community guidelines.

How to structure a multilingual topic

To help everyone navigate the forum easily, please follow this format when creating or contributing to a non-English topic:

- Add the appropriate language tag (e.g. *français, español, deutsche*, etc.). If you're not sure whether a tag exists yet, no worries—create one.
- Write your topic title in the language used in the topic.
- Keep the entire discussion in the same language within that topic.

Why this matters

By creating space for multilingual conversations, we:

[D4.5 IPSP Registry]

- Make the forum more welcoming and inclusive
- Help users express themselves more clearly
- Encourage broader participation from across the community

Looking forward to seeing more multilingual conversations here!

4 Guidelines for moderators

<https://forum.diamas.org/t/guidelines-for-moderators/92>

Thank you for taking on the responsibility of maintaining a welcoming, inclusive, and constructive community space. As a moderator, you play a key role in shaping the discussions, engaging with members, and ensuring that our forum remains respectful and aligned with our community standards.

You are free to select a category to moderate and are expected to be proactive—this includes creating topics, engaging with members and keeping conversations constructive.

Moderation is not a permanent commitment: you can take on this role for a set period of time based on your availability and interest.

Your contribution is essential to fostering a dynamic, welcoming and inclusive community! This guide outlines your responsibilities, available tools, and best practices to help you succeed in your role.

[Title] Moderator responsibilities

Your primary responsibilities include:

Upholding the community guidelines:

- Ensure users adhere to the forum’s rules and values (see our [Community guidelines](#)).
- Moderate the discussion by managing posts to address off-topic discussions, behaviours such as harassment, spam, or hate speech.
- Review reported issues and when necessary, apply appropriate actions to maintain a positive environment. This may include issuing warnings, editing, or removing posts.

Encouraging positive interactions:

- Facilitate discussions that focus on ideas, not individuals.
- Support one another’s work and foster a culture of respect and collaboration.
- Promote openness and transparency to maintain constructive dialogue.

Maintaining impartiality:

- Moderate objectively by considering the context from which the respondent comes from and regardless of personal biases or relationships with users.
- Consider cultural and linguistic diversity when evaluating discussions.

Monitoring and feedback:

- Participate in regular moderation reviews to share experiences and improve moderation practices.
- Encourage community feedback to refine the moderation process.

[Title] Moderator code of conduct

As a moderator, you represent the EDCH Forum and must adhere to our standards of conduct:

- **Be agreeable** – Maintain a calm and neutral tone, and avoid escalating conflicts.
- **Respect each other** – Ensure all voices are heard, even in disagreement.
- **Consult with peers** – For complex or controversial cases, discuss the situation with admins.
- **Confidentiality** – Keep all moderation discussions private and never share sensitive information.
- **Accountability** – Document major actions in the moderation logs for transparency.

Misuse of moderation privileges may result in warnings/coaching from admin, or temporary/permanent removal from the moderator role.

[Title] Communication between moderators and admin team

As a moderator, you play a key role in maintaining a welcoming and productive forum. To ensure smooth collaboration, regular communication with the admin team is essential.

Best practices for moderator-admin communication:

- **Report serious issues promptly** – If a situation escalates beyond your capacity, inform the admin team as soon as possible.
- **Seek guidance when unsure** – If you're uncertain about how to handle a specific issue, discuss it with the admins before taking action.
- **Participate in moderator discussions** – Engage in periodic check-ins or meetings with the admin team to share insights, raise concerns, and improve moderation strategies.
- **Maintain transparency** – Keep the admin team informed of any significant moderation actions, policy enforcement, or recurring issues within your category.

Staff category

The Staff category is a private section of the forum, accessible exclusively to moderators and administrators. It serves as a centralised space where staff members can:

- Discuss ongoing moderation actions and share observations.
- Document internal policies, procedures, and guidelines for consistency.
- Coordinate responses to complex situations that require team input.

Moderators are encouraged to use this category to keep everyone informed and aligned.

Channels

Channels are group conversations that can be open to all users or limited to specific members. The “staff” channel is visible – and limited – to all moderators and members of the admin team, and serves as a convenient space to discuss matters that don’t necessarily warrant a dedicated topic within a category.

Watching your category

Moderators are also encouraged to follow the category they moderate by clicking on the bell icon at the top right of the category page, and by choosing the “watching option”. This ensures you receive notifications for new posts and can respond promptly.

[Title] Moderator’s daily tasks

Discourse provides robust tools to help you manage the forum effectively. Below is an overview of key tools and how to use them:

Managing account requests

One of your key responsibilities is to verify account requests. When reviewing these requests, ensure that the user meets one of the following criteria:

1. The user’s organisation is listed in the EDCH Registry.
2. The user is involved in the European Diamond OA publishing landscape.

Please verify the relevant information before approving any account requests to maintain the integrity of the forum. If you plan to deny a user’s request or are uncertain about their compliance, please consult an admin before making any decisions.

To deny access to a user, please select **“Delete user”** and make sure to send a follow-up email explaining the reason for the decision.

Suggested email template: outside of scope (with APC)

[Email template]

Suggested email template: lack of information

[Email template]

Engagement with New Users

For any new user who is not listed in the European Diamond Capacity Hub Registry, please send them the following message template to encourage registration. This helps us ensure the Forum is aligned with the Registry and its objectives.

Suggested message template to send via direct message:

[Email template]

Managing content

As a moderator, you have several tools to keep the forum organised and user-friendly:

1. Edit posts and topics:

When to edit:

- To correct minor issues, such as spelling mistakes, formatting problems, or inappropriate language.
- To clean up a topic, for instance, when tags are missing or incorrect (e.g. forgetting a language tag or adding irrelevant ones).

These small edits help maintain clarity and consistency across the forum, making content easier to find and engage with.

How to edit:

- Simply click the pencil button below the post and make necessary changes.

[Image: Edit a post]

It's recommended to leave a note indicating the reason for the edit. Do not edit a post to alter the user's meaning. If a post is unclear, consider requesting clarification under the post directly from the user.

[Image: Inform the user of the edit]

2. Move topics to the right category:

When to move topics:

- If a topic belongs in a different category, move it to the appropriate category, or create a new one if needed.

How to move:

- Simply click the pencil button below the post and choose the correct category.

Provide a brief explanation in the topic to inform the user about the move.

[Image: Move a topic to another category]

3. Delete posts:

When to delete:

- Posts that are spam, contain hate speech, personal attacks, or violate major community guidelines should be deleted.

Avoid deleting posts without clear justification. Instead, use editing or moving tools when appropriate.

How to delete:

[D4.5 IPSP Registry]

- Click on the “Delete” button. If the post is flagged, consider discussing the deletion with other moderators/admins before proceeding, especially for borderline cases.

Please inform the user about the deletion and the reason for it.

[Image: Delete a post]

Handling reports

Community members are encouraged to report any inappropriate behavior or issues they encounter directly to the moderators of the relevant category.

As a moderator, your role is to review reported issues and take appropriate action based on the situation. Follow the steps outlined in the “Levels of intervention for heated, difficult, or non-productive discussions” section to ensure a fair and consistent approach.

- Contacting the user privately to clarify concerns.
- Editing or removing problematic content when necessary.
- Escalating serious issues to the admin team if further action is required.

Maintain a record of all reported issues, actions taken, and outcomes to ensure transparency and consistency in moderation decisions.

Handling flags

Our forum guidelines do not rely on the flagging system for reporting inappropriate behavior. However, if flags are used, moderators should handle them as follows:

- Review flagged content in the “Review Queue.”
- Evaluate whether the flag is valid. If valid, take action (e.g., edit, delete, or issue a warning). If invalid, dismiss the flag.

[Image: Review flags]

User management

- Access user profiles to view their activity, trust-level, and past interactions.
- Temporarily silence or suspend accounts of users violating guidelines.

Logs and Records

- Use the moderation logs to track actions taken by moderators and admins for transparency.
- Access user reports for a comprehensive history of flagged content.

[Title] Levels of intervention for heated, difficult, or non-productive discussion

If discussion in a topic is no longer productive or discussion is no longer focused on the topic, but instead on “attacking” other users instead of ideas, moderators should step in.

Moderation actions should be proportional to the severity of the issue. Follow these steps when addressing problematic behavior:

1. Friendly reminder

Many times, a simple reminder is enough to solve the issue. Politely remind users of the guidelines when they're talking in circles or when minor issues arise. Use the post admin wrench to mark the post a staff post, this indicates to users that the post is the official position of the EDCH.

Example: "Hi [username], please remember to stay on-topic as per our forum rules (add a link to our guidelines). Thank you!"

2. Set a topic timer

If a staff post does not resolve the issue, or if the discussion becomes so heated that a reminder is unlikely to help, you can temporarily pause the topic.

To do this, use the topic admin wrench to set a topic timer. This will immediately close the topic, preventing new posts, and display a notice when the topic will reopen.

[Image: Set a topic timer]

3. Set slow mode

If users are engaging in rapid-fire replies, you can encourage more thoughtful conversation by engaging slow mode, which will set a waiting period for each user between replies.

To enable slow mode on a topic, use the topic admin wrench and select set slow mode. Then configure slow mode by selecting how long you'd like users to have to wait between posts and when you'd like slow mode to be automatically disabled. Waiting period options range from 10 minutes to 24 hours, with a custom option available. Automatic disabling of slow mode can be scheduled for a few hours to a few months in the future, with a custom option also available.

[Image: Set a slow mode]

4. Official warning

Issue an official warning for repeated or moderate violations. Use private messages to communicate the issue and suggest corrective actions.

5. Temporary silence users

Temporarily silence users for a specific period of time for serious violations or repeated offenses. Inform them about the duration and reason for the suspension.

Always consult with admins before silencing a user.

[Image: Silence a user]

Silenced users are prevented from creating new topics, posts, flags or PMs on the site. They can still perform other actions such as liking posts, reading threads, replying to PMs, etc. They can also communicate with moderators via PM, so you can continue to communicate with them to try and resolve the behaviour.

[D4.5 IPSP Registry]

6. Suspension

Reserve suspensions for extreme cases, such as persistent trolling, hate speech, or illegal activities.

Always consult with admins before issuing a suspension ban.

[Image: Suspend a user]

Suspended users are prevented from logging in, and thus from completing any actions on the forum. A suspension is the strongest possible recourse you have for a user and should be used sparingly. You may want to suspend the user for a short period of time first, and if the user returns and continues the behaviour, increase the suspension time.

Thank you!

Thank you for your dedication and service to the EDCH Forum! Moderation is a challenging but rewarding responsibility. By following these guidelines, you'll help foster a vibrant, respectful, and thriving community.

If you have any further questions about how things should work here, open a new topic in Staff and let's discuss! If there's a critical or urgent issue that can't be handled by a meta topic or flag, contact the admin team.

